

DEMO CASES

ITALIAN CASE STUDY

Bagnolo in Piano, ReggioEmilia

Italian Case Study

Location: Bagnolo in Piano, Reggio Emilia, Italy.

Year of construction: 1985

Type of building: large multifamily house

Distribution: on 2 staircases, 5 floors

(Ground level and attic no climatized. Levels 1, 2, 3 appartaments)

Gross heating volume: 2,340 m³

Net surface of about: 636 m²

Units: 12 units (6 units of 43 m², 6 units of 63 m²)

Window to Wall Ratio: 18%

S/V: 0.63

CASE STUDY

Italian Case Study - Envelope technologies

Requalification of the opaque envelope

building site

construction activity

Requalification of the transparent envelope

replacement of the existing glass with a new one

gaskets substitution

roller shutter box insulation

Italian Case Study - Technical systems

Heat pump and thermal storage

indoor unit

outdoor unit

Thermal storage with PCM

Hydronic and electrical distribution

hydronic distribution

electric distribution

PV tiles

Power conversion and management (MIMO)

IoT Devices

Smart fan coil units and smart DHW

Italian Case Study - Results of retrofit intervention

CASE STUDY

FRENCH CASE STUDY

Bagnolo in Pinao, Lyon

French Case Study

Location: Saint-Priest, Lyon, France.

Year of construction: 1960

Type of building: multifamily building

Distribution: on 2 stairwells, 2 floors

(Underground level and attic no climatized. Levels Ground, 1 appartamets)

Gross heating volume: 4,200 m³

Net surface of about: 1'118 m²

Units: 26 units (dwelling average are 43 m²)

Window to Wall Ratio: 11%

S/V: 0.66

CASE STUDY

France Case Study - Envelope technologies

Requalification of the opaque envelope

building site

construction activity

Windows refurbishment

outdoor

indoor

Heat pump and thermal storage
outdoor unit

Hydronic and electrical distribution

France Case Study - Results of retrofit intervention

South

East

North

West

About HEART

The Holistic Energy and Architectural Retrofit Toolkit (HEART) brings together different components and technologies that can transform existing buildings into smart buildings, thus contributing to the Renovation Wave in order to decarbonise Europe's building stock. In developing this toolkit, the project advances and improves energy efficiency and the use of renewable energies in buildings across Europe, particularly in Central and Southern Europe, where climate change is leading to increased electricity consumption during the summer and winter seasons.

Get in touch

 <https://heartproject.eu/>

 sudhanshu@revolve.media

 HEARTProjectEU

 HEART Project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 768921.